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Press Release

Smart Maritime And Underwater Guardian

The **SMAUG** (Smart Maritime And Underwater Guardian) project has officially started! SMAUG is funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe Research & Innovation programme, with a starting date of **October 1, 2023**, and a duration of 36 months.

The constant increase in **maritime environment activity** requires strong and efficient **port security procedures** to be implemented. This is particularly crucial for the identification and surveillance of both legitimate and illicit operations in border, coastal, and port regions. New techniques in drug smuggling and illegal activities taking place in the maritime environment are currently generating **more challenges for law enforcement**, as current detection means may often be no longer effective, while technological updates and improvements in prevention mechanisms are deemed mandatory. To combat these issues, countertrafficking organisations demand significant penetration, whereas sometimes they lack resources. As much as illegal activity is a focus for maritime security, **monitoring legal activity is also paramount**, especially concerning customs, operational and border management.

The **primary goal** of SMAUG, hence, is to improve and enhance the security of ports and their entrance routes, leveraging the power of Artificial Intelligence (AI), using an integrated system capable of providing data concerning threat detection and analysis between 3 main elements: *ports security infrastructure, advanced underwater detection systems and surveillance vessels*. Underwater detection and location will

be performed by 4 primary methods: acoustic detection, where a series of hydrophones will listen for sounds emitted by small underwater vehicles and will be processed by artificial intelligence methods, rapid sonar hull scan, used to scan ships hulls and perform harbour floor scanning, high-resolution sonar inspection, to inspect objects in water with poor visibility and collective autonomous location, where a swarm of autonomous underwater vehicles will act cooperatively. The combination of these tools will allow SMAUG to prompt solutions capable of detecting possible threats to infrastructure or vessels, as well as identify vessels with concealed goods.

The SMAUG project consists of **22 highly** experienced partners who will provide their expertise and knowledge to generate impactful results through the project, achieving the maximum outreach. More precisely, the consortium includes **Universities, Research Centres, SMEs, Law Enforcement Agencies, Public authorities, Coastal / Border guards** and **Private organisations** who will collaboratively work to achieve the SMAUG goals throughout the next **36 months**.

Stay tuned with the SMAUG project!

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